

Numerical Solution of a Class of Fractional Optimal Control Problems by Using Bernoulli Wavelets Approximation

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Abstract

A numerical method for solving a class of fractional optimal control problems (FOCPs) is presented. First the given problem is transformed into an equivalent variational problem. Then using the Bernoulli wavelet basis and operational matrix of fractional integration, the problem is reduced to a system of algebraic equations. Finally, this system is solved using the Gauss quadrature formula and Newton's iterative method.

Keywords: Bernoulli wavelet, Fractional optimal control problems, Gauss-Legendre integration formula, Caputo fractional derivative.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, researchers in the areas of science, engineering, physics, mathematics and finance have drawn attention to the dynamics of many systems that can be described more precisely by using fractional differential equations [?]. Meanwhile, for the state of the art on fractional optimal control, one can see the recently published book [?].

2 Basic definitions

In this section we present some basic definitions needed in the following parts of the paper.

2.1 The fractional derivative and integral

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as ([?],[?])

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases}$$

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For the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral we have

$$I^\nu t^\beta = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+\nu+1)} t^{\nu+\beta}, \quad \beta > -1.$$

Definition 2.2. Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as ([?],[?])

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have

$$D^\nu I^\nu f(t) = f(t), \quad I^\nu D^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

2.2 Bernoulli wavelet

The Bernoulli wavelet $\psi_{nm}(t) = \psi(k, \hat{n}, m, t)$ involves four arguments, $\hat{n} = n - 1$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, k is assumed any positive integer, m is the degree of the Bernoulli polynomials and t is the normalized time. They are defined on the interval $[0, 1)$ by [?]

$$\psi_{n,m}(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \tilde{\beta}_m(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$\tilde{\beta}_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{(-1)^{m-1}(m!)^2}{(2m)!} \alpha_{2m}}} \beta_m(t), & m > 0, \end{cases}$$

and $m = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$. Here $\beta_m(t)$ are the well-known Bernoulli polynomials of order m [?]. Also, we let

$$B(t) = [\beta_0(t), \beta_1(t), \dots, \beta_{M-1}(t)]^T, \quad \Psi(t) = [\psi_1(t), \psi_2(t), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1}M}(t)]^T.$$

3 Operational matrix of the fractional integration

The Bernoulli wavelets can be expanded into an M terms Bernoulli polynomials as

$$\Psi_{2^{k-1}M \times 1}(t) = \Phi_{2^{k-1}M \times M} B_{M \times 1}(t),$$

where Φ is the transformation matrix of the Bernoulli wavelet to the Bernoulli polynomials [?]. The fractional integral of Bernoulli polynomials vector can be written as

$$I^\nu B(t) = F^{(\nu)} B(t),$$

where $F^{(\nu)}$ is given in [?]. Therefore, the Bernoulli wavelets operational matrix of the fractional integration $P^{(\nu)}(I^\nu \Psi(t) = P^{(\nu)} \Psi(t))$, that is

$$P^{(\nu)} = \Phi F^{(\nu)} \Phi^{-1}.$$

4 Problem statement and approximation method

Consider the FOCP

$$\min(\max) \quad J[u] = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), u(t)) dt, \tag{1}$$

subject to

$$D^\nu x(t) = g(t, x(t)) + b(t)u(t), \quad n-1 \leq \nu \leq n, \quad n = 2, 3, \dots \tag{2}$$

$$x(0) = x_0, \quad x'(0) = x_1, \dots, \quad x^{([\nu]-1)}(0) = x_{[\nu]-1}.$$

Here f, g and $b \neq 0$ are smooth functions of their arguments. Computing the control function from relation (??) and substituting into the performance index J yields

$$\min(\max) J[x] = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), \frac{1}{b(t)}(D^\nu x(t) - g(t, x(t))))dt, \quad (3)$$

$$x(0) = x_0, x'(0) = x_1, \dots, x^{(\lceil \nu \rceil - 1)}(0) = x_{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1}.$$

Now we solve the optimization problem (??) via Bernoulli wavelets approximation. First, we approximate $D^\nu x(t)$ and $x(t)$ as

$$D^\nu x(t) \simeq C^T \Psi(t), \quad x(t) \simeq C^T P^\nu \Psi(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i. \quad (4)$$

By substituting the approximations (??) in the performance index (??), our aim is to optimize the functional of $\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M$ variables, $c_j; j = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{m}$ as

$$\min(\max) J[C] = \int_0^1 f(t, C^T P^\nu \Psi(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i, \frac{1}{b(t)}(C^T \Psi(t) - g(t, C^T P^\nu \Psi(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i)))dt.$$

For simplicity, we let

$$\min(\max) J[C] = \int_0^1 Q(t, C)dt, \quad (5)$$

where

$$Q(t, C) = f(t, C^T P^\nu \Psi(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i, \frac{1}{b(t)}(C^T \Psi(t) - g(t, C^T P^\nu \Psi(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i))).$$

The Gaussian quadrature formula is used to approximate the integration in Eq. (??). We get

$$\tilde{J}[c] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^M \omega_i Q\left(\frac{\tau_i + 1}{2}, C\right), \quad (6)$$

where $\tau_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, M$; are zeros of Legendre polynomial $P_M(t)$ and $\omega_i = \frac{-2}{(M+1)P'_M(\tau_i)P_{M+1}(\tau_i)}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$. The necessary conditions for extremum of $\tilde{J}$ are given by

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{J}}{\partial c_i}[C] = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{m}.$$

The above relations can be solved for C using the Newton's iterative method.

5 Illustrative test problems

Example 5.1. Consider the following minimization problem [?]

$$\min J = \int_0^1 [(x(t) - t^2)^2 + (u(t) + t^4 - \frac{20t^{\frac{9}{10}}}{9\Gamma(\frac{9}{10})})^2]dt,$$

$$D^{1.1}x(t) = t^2x(t) + u(t), \quad x(0) = x'(0) = 0.$$

For this problem $x(t) = t^2$ and $u(t) = \frac{20t^{\frac{9}{10}}}{9\Gamma(\frac{9}{10})} - t^4$, minimize the performance index J is zero. In Table 1, the approximate values of minimum J using Legendre polynomials and Bernoulli wavelets with $k = 2$ for different values of m are listed.

Example 5.2. Consider the following minimization problem [?]

$$\min J = \int_0^1 [e^t(x(t) - t^4 + t - 1)^2 + (1 + t^2)(u(t) + 1 - t + t^4 - \frac{8000t^{\frac{21}{10}}}{77\Gamma(\frac{10}{10})})^2]dt,$$

$$D^{1.9}x(t) = x(t) + u(t), \quad x(0) = 1, \quad x'(0) = -1.$$

For this problem $x(t) = 1 - t + t^4$, minimize the performance index J is zero. Table 2 presents the approximate values of minimum J using Legendre polynomials and Bernoulli wavelets for $k = 2$ and different values of m .

Table 1: Estimated values of J with $k = 2, n = m + 1$ for Example 1.

m	Ref. [?]	Present method
3	6.07530×10^{-6}	1.10996×10^{-6}
4	1.67255×10^{-6}	3.20698×10^{-7}
5	5.91532×10^{-7}	1.18416×10^{-7}
7	1.21966×10^{-7}	2.47672×10^{-8}
8	7.03371×10^{-8}	1.35155×10^{-8}

 Table 2: Estimated values of J with $k = 2, n = m$ for Example 2.

m	Ref. [?]	Present method
3	8.93768×10^{-6}	8.10730×10^{-7}
4	5.42028×10^{-7}	1.56726×10^{-8}
5	6.77757×10^{-8}	1.99273×10^{-9}
7	2.84624×10^{-9}	1.60947×10^{-10}

Example 5.3. Consider the following minimization problem [?]

$$\min J = \int_0^1 [(x(t) - t^{\frac{5}{2}})^4 + (1 + t^2)(u(t) + t^6 - \frac{15\sqrt{\pi}t}{8})^2] dt,$$

$$D^{1.5}x(t) = tx^2(t) + u(t), \quad x(0) = x'(0) = 0.$$

For this problem $x(t) = t^{\frac{5}{2}}$, minimize the performance index J is zero. Table 3 presents the approximate values of minimum J using Legendre polynomials and Bernoulli wavelets for $k = 2$ and $m = 3$.

 Table 3: Estimated values of J with $k = 2, n = m$ for Example 3.

m	Ref. [?]	Present method
3	2.2777×10^{-7}	6.42449×10^{-10}

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